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GENNARO DI PRISCO & PAOLA CONTI

BEEVESUVIUS: POLLINATORS AND ECOSYSTEM SERVICES
IN THE VESUVIO NATIONAL PARK

*Beevesuvius: impollinatori e servizi ecosistemici
nel Parco Nazionale del Vesuvio*

The Vesuvio National Park (VNP), an area of great geological and historical interest, has been established to preserve the values of the territory, use suitable means to allow a correct integration between man and environment, promote environmental education and scientific research activities.

In this context, the VNP is implementing monitoring and research actions which will take place in its territories. More specifically, these actions involve methodologies for faunal studies of pollinating insects (Apoidea and Lepidoptera), evaluation of ecosystem services related to pollination in agroecosystems, management of honey bee colonies for the biomonitoring of environmental pollutants. These activities include sampling through geo-referenced transects and traps, dry preparation, and taxonomic identification of Apoidea and Lepidoptera samples, morpho-molecular analysis, data analysis and dissemination. Here will be described and discussed all the experimental design and possible outcomes.

Authors' Address — G. DI PRISCO – Institute for Sustainable Plant Protection – The Italian National Research Council (IPSP-CNR) Piazzale Enrico Fermi, 1 – 80055 Portici (Napoli, Italy), e-mail: gennaro.diprisco@ipsp.cnr.it; P. CONTI – Ente Parco Nazionale del Vesuvio, Via Palazzo del Principe presso il castello mediceo – 80044 Ottaviano (Napoli, Italy); e-mail: pconti@epnv.it

